

Gas diffusion nanocomposite layer with enhanced mass transport with surface functionalization by laser irradiation

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Introduction

Gas and water mass transfer remain significant challenges in **proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs)**, making the surface properties and structural configuration of the **gas diffusion layer (GDL)** critical for performance. A newly proposed **gas diffusion nanocomposite layer (GDNL)** features a **multi-walled carbon nanotube/polytetrafluoroethylene (MWCNT/PTFE) nanocomposite film with a laser-perforated pattern filled with carbon black/PTFE (CB/PTFE) microporous material**, forming a **hydrophilic–superhydrophobic columnar interface**. In this design, laser irradiation induces hydrophilicity along the inner walls of the perforations, directing water transport through the hydrophilic interface. Meanwhile, the superhydrophobic CB/PTFE filling channels gas transport inside the structure and repels water outward, ensuring separated and efficient pathways for gas and water movement. **This unique columnar interface in the LPM-GDNL design results in ~40% and ~50% improvements in current and power density** in the concentration loss region at relative humidity levels of 50% and 100%, respectively, compared to conventional commercial carbon paper GDLs.

Experiment

Film fabrication

- MWCNT and PTFE were mixed with a dispersant.
- A film was prepared by vacuum filtration.
- The fabricated film was sintered by hot pressing at 350 °C.

Laser perforation and MPL coating

- Holes (60 x 110 μm) were perforated at 200 μm intervals using a laser.
- CB/PTFE MPL was coated on the perforated film and sintered.

GDL properties

- Laser perforation reduced the conductivity of the film, but CB/PTFE coating restored conductivity and increased compressibility significantly.
- LPM-GDNL exhibited much higher through-plane gas permeability than commercial GDLs due to vertical perforations and porous MPL coating.
- Water breakthrough pressure was greatly reduced in LPM-GDNL, indicating enhanced water removal through the hydrophilic interface.

PEMFC performances

- LPM-GDNL showed significantly improved PEMFC performance under both RH50 and RH100 by combining enhanced conductivity with a hydrophilic–superhydrophobic columnar interface.
- This structure reduced ohmic and mass transport resistance, as confirmed by EIS analysis, leading to better charge transfer and water management.
- Compared to commercial GDLs, LPM-GDNL achieved up to 59% higher power density, demonstrating the effectiveness of combining perforation and surface energy control.

Results & Discussion

Characterization

- Laser irradiation produced uniformly spaced, truncated cone-shaped holes with a bumpy texture in the C50P50 film.
- These holes were filled with CB/PTFE slurry, forming a porous MPL layer that provides gas pathways and firmly anchors in place.

- Laser irradiation increased surface hydrophilicity and tension by changing chemistry and microstructure.
- This enabled unique gas and water transport through a nano-micro hybrid interface.

- XPS analysis showed that laser irradiation reduced C=C and C-F bond intensities while increasing oxygen and nitrogen content.
- These compositional changes enhanced surface hydrophilicity and altered the nanocomposite's chemical structure.

Conclusions

- Laser-perforated MWCNT/PTFE films with CB/PTFE filling created a hydrophilic–superhydrophobic columnar structure that improved water removal and gas transport.
- This design lowered electrical resistance and enhanced PEMFC performance by reducing ohmic and mass transport losses.
- Further optimization of composition and perforation is expected to boost mass transport even more, supporting sustainable hydrogen energy.

References

- T. Eom et al., 'A gas diffusion nanocomposite layer with a hydrophilic–superhydrophobic columnar interface for enhanced water and gas transport', *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2025,13, 17963-17975